

A new approach to measuring angular-dependent transmittance values of extended complex fenestration systems with a near field goniophotometer

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ABSTRACT

The knowledge of angle-dependent transmittance values is crucial for many areas in the built environment, such as visual and thermal comfort assessment or energy demand calculation. Measurement devices used for complex fenestration systems are typically far field goniophotometers, which require a large distance between sample and detector. As alternative to conventional far field devices, a near field goniophotometer to measure angle-dependent transmittance values of shading systems was developed. The new device is aimed at extended shading systems with structural elements, such as blind systems. This is realized by combining large-area detectors with an angle filter of a specific angular sensitivity curve. The measurement principle and prototypical setup are explained and requirements of divergence of the light source and the detector are formulated followed by a thorough discussion of the results. A comparison between near field and far field measurements was carried out. A raytracing simulation model that replicates the measurement procedure was used for comparison with measured data. All measurements were carried out with an artificial light source and fixed incidence angles in normal direction to the sample. The comparison of measured and simulated transmittance showed low absolute errors. The scattering effect of a mirror lamella found in the measurement could be replicated by the simulation. Some differences in absolute transmittance of the mirror lamella, which might be caused by effects that are not covered in the simulation model, were found between measurement and simulation. A qualitative and quantitative analysis of errors and uncertainty was carried out.

1. Introduction

The angle-dependent transmittance through the transparent or translucent area of a building envelope is an important property for many application areas. When assessing solar gains through fenestration systems for energy balance calculations, the inward exittance of transmitted solar radiation is typically integrated over the space. For thermal and visual comfort studies that consider the specific location in the space, the distribution of transmitted radiation within the evaluated building zone must be taken into account. For example, for the assessment of visual comfort and daylight availability at specific locations, it is

mandatory to know from which direction and in which quantity light enters the space. Current standards such as EN 17037 [1] offer different methods to rate daylight availability and to estimate annual insolation of indoor spaces, but still show certain shortcomings when light-scattering fenestration systems (also called complex fenestration systems, CFS) are present. In addition to visual comfort, there are other research areas that require detailed information about incident radiation on specific surfaces beyond the spectrum of visible light, such as advanced thermal comfort studies that inquire into the effect of short-wave radiation on the body (parts) of building occupants [2] and light redirecting shading systems aiming at directional selectivity [3].

The angle-dependent transmittance through building envelopes is

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Nomenclature

D_P	Dimension of the sample
D_A	Dimension of the aperture
D_S	Dimension of the structural unit (within sample)
D_{LP}	Distance light source to sample
D_D	Dimension of the detector
$D_{D,FF}$	Dimension of the detector of far field
D_{PD}	Distance sample to detector
$D_{PD,FF}$	Distance sample to detector of far field
$D_{PD,NF}$	Distance sample to detector of near field
SR	Spectral response of detector [A/W]
θ'	Polar incidence angle of light source
φ'	Azimuthal incidence angle of light source
θ	Polar angle of detector/polar exitance angle
φ	Azimuthal angle of detector/azimuthal exitance angle
$\Delta\theta_{\max,AF}$	Polar acceptance angle of the angle filter

$\Delta\varphi_{\max,AF}$	Azimuthal acceptance angle of the angle filter
$\Delta\theta_{LS}$	Polar divergence angle of the light source
$\Delta\varphi_{LS}$	Azimuthal divergence angle of the light source
τ	Transmittance
ρ	Reflectance
α	Absorptance

Abbreviations

UV	Ultraviolet radiation (300 nm–380 nm)
VIS	Visible light (380 nm–780 nm)
IR	Shortwave infrared (780 nm–2500 nm)
BTDF	Bidirectional transmittance distribution function
BRDF	Bidirectional reflectance distribution function
BSDF	Bidirectional scattering distribution function
CFS	Complex fenestration systems
FWHM	Full-Width at Half Maximum

typically formulated as a bidirectional transmittance distribution function (BTDF). Together with the bidirectional reflectance distribution functions (BRDF) of the outside and the inside of the fenestration, the BTDF forms the bidirectional scattering distribution functions (BSDF) – a description of light transport via the building envelope between any pair of directions [4–7]. The characterization of scattering properties of surface properties using BSDF in general [8], as well as the application for characterizing daylighting or shading systems [9] has been the subject of active research for many years. Nowadays, many simulation tools rely on BSDFs for annual calculations of solar transmittance for buildings with complex fenestration systems [10].

BSDFs can be generated numerically with existing tools either for predefined, typical shading geometries (e.g., Window (LBL) [11]) or with raytracing software (e.g., Radiance genBSDF [12,13] for arbitrary geometries. In both cases, not only the geometry of the shading system but also the exact local optical properties of its elements are mandatory. If either geometry or optical properties are unknown or impossible to determine empirically, measurements of the shading system's BSDF are required. Even if numerical generation of BSDFs using geometry information and local optical properties is possible, direct measurements inform about the validity of numerically generated results. Within the IEA SHC Task 61/EBC Annex 77, international experts summarized existing approaches for BSDF characterization of daylighting systems [14] and inspired the current standardization efforts by ISO/CIE CD 25176 [15].

In practice, extended complex fenestration systems with structural patterns that exceed the range of several millimeters are difficult to measure with most existing goniophotometers due to the small aperture of the devices. Furthermore, typical goniophotometer measurements on large samples can be time- and cost-intensive. Therefore, there is an obvious need for affordable solutions to quantitatively assess the solar transmittance properties of complex fenestration systems with large structures.

In the following sections, the authors describe a prototype of a novel instrument to measure angle-dependent transmittance values on extended systems in the nearfield. The requirements of the device with respect to geometry and components are explained in Section 2. A preliminary validation study was carried out by comparing near field versus far field measurements (Section 3) as well as by comparing near field measurements with simulation approaches (Section 4). An error analysis was carried out in Section 5.

2. Methodology – near field goniophotometer

The development of a near field goniophotometer poses a major

challenge: at close distance between sample and detector, it is difficult to limit the detected photons to the specific angular range to obtain the desired angular resolution. These challenges always occur when a much larger distance between object and detector compared to the size of the measurement spot, given either by the size of the irradiation area or by the area over which the detector senses flux, cannot be realized. The proposed design addresses this challenge by using large-area detectors consisting of an angle filter and a light sensor. To be valid, the transmittance values measured by the novel setup need to correspond to those determined using goniophotometer setups in the far field. The main aspects of the measurement procedure are described below. Details and the metrological requirements can be found in VDI-EE 2068 [16], which has been established by the authors.

The definition of polar and azimuthal angles θ' , φ' , θ , φ adheres to the following systematic: The sample lies in the x-y plane. The positive x-axis is the reference for azimuthal angles φ and φ' . The sample's surface normal points towards the direction of incidence as positive z-axis. θ is defined as the polar angle between the detector and the negative direction of z-axis, θ' is defined as the polar angle between the incident direction of the light source and the positive direction of z-axis.

2.1. Principle and setup

Fig. 1 schematically shows the components and the basic geometry of a measurement setup that uses the new measurement principle of near field goniophotometry. The angle-dependent transmittance values are measured with a collimated light source that irradiates a representative area of the sample with a standardized spectral distribution. The angle-dependent transmitted radiant power is measured on a large-area detector in the near field which is equipped with an angle filter on its front side. The ratio of the transmitted and incident radiant power results in the unweighted angle-dependent transmittance values of the representative sample area. The detection always covers effective solid angles that correspond to cones with certain opening angles. Thus, the angle-dependent transmittance values have to be weighted with these effective solid angles in order to be comparable (see Section 3.3). The effective size of the solid angles depends on the geometry and the related angle selectivity of the angle filter used (see Section 2.4).

1. Area of the light source at distance D_{LP} from the sample.
2. Maximum angular divergence of the light source $\Delta\theta_{LS}$ or $\Delta\varphi_{LS}$.
3. Sample with dimension D_P as well as dimension D_S of the extended structural units.
4. Sample placement location with a circular aperture of aperture diameter D_A .

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the near field transmittance measurement setup [16]. Note, that the setup contains only one detector – the two detectors in the schematic drawing visualize the variable positioning of this single detector.

5. Area detector with detector dimension D_D placed at angular position 1 (θ_1, φ_1).
6. Area detector (5) placed at angular position 2 (θ_2, φ_2).
7. Angle filter with maximum acceptance angles $\Delta\theta_{max,AF}$ and $\Delta\varphi_{max,AF}$ being part of the detector.
8. Light sensor as a part of the detector.
9. Angular range $\theta_1 \pm \Delta\theta_{max,AF}$ and $\varphi_1 \pm \Delta\varphi_{max,AF}$, within which transmitted rays reach the sensor at angular position 1 (θ_1, φ_1).
10. Angular range $\theta_2 \pm \Delta\theta_{max,AF}$ and $\varphi_2 \pm \Delta\varphi_{max,AF}$, within which transmitted rays reach the sensor at angular position 2 (θ_2, φ_2).

Fig. 2 shows the prototype, which was used for the proof-of-concept measurements presented in this paper. The dimensions of the distance D_{PD} between sample and detector and distance D_{LP} between light source and sample are 29 cm and 76 cm, respectively. The pendulum can be moved in 2.5° steps and the sample can be rotated for a continuous azimuthal variation. The aspect ratio of the angle filter is set to 1:12; the resulting FWHM is approximately 6° .

2.2. Wavelength range

The required range of wavelength depends on the application area. The light source and sensors used in the detector must cover the entire range of wavelength to be considered. For example, the spectrum of

visible light from 380 to 780 nm, according to EN 410 [17], is required in (day-)lighting design, while to generate data for the energy assessment of façade systems, a larger wavelength range is required, typically covering the spectrum from 300 to 2500 nm according to EN 410 [17]. Depending on the requirements of the application, angle-dependent measurements can either be carried out in a particular wavelength range in isolation (e.g., VIS only) or they can combine several spectral ranges (e.g., UV + VIS + IR).

However, it cannot be assumed a priori that the scattering behavior of the investigated sample is identical in all spectral ranges, especially when larger wavelength ranges are considered. The angle-dependent transmittance values derived through the measurements represent spectrally integrated values for the corresponding spectral ranges. Therefore, wavelengths that are not included in the investigated spectrum must be eliminated either on the source side or on the detector side.

2.3. Divergence and irradiance of light source

The prototype of the near field goniophotometer was developed so that the light source irradiates an area of the test sample that extends beyond the aperture in all directions. The light source generates a constant radiant power for the duration of the measurement. The temporal stability and uniformity of the irradiance are in accordance with the standard IEC 60904-9 [18] with classes A to C. The light source used in the prototype provides a stability of 1 % and a uniformity of 5 %.

The light source and its arrangement in the test setup are such that at least 95 % of the incident radiometric flux on the test specimen does not exceed an angular divergence of $\Delta\theta_{LS}/\Delta\varphi_{LS} = \pm 3^\circ$ relative to the investigated direction of incidence (φ', θ'). No particular requirements were imposed on the irradiance level of the light source for determining the angle-dependent transmittance, but the irradiance of the light source and the dynamic range of the detector must be matched.

The light source used for the prototype is an Abet Sun 2000 sun simulator with 1000 W/m^2 collimated light, a $16 \text{ cm} \times 16 \text{ cm}$ large laterally uniform light field, and a class A AM1.5G spectrum in the spectral range from about 380 nm to 1100 nm. The spectrum of the light source is shown in Fig. 3a. It fulfills all requirements stated in VDI-EE 2068 [16]. In the test setup, the position of the light source was static, i.e., no variation of incidence angles (φ', θ') was considered. In general, this variation in incidence angles can be realized by tilting the sample within the test plane.

2.4. Detector with sensor and angle filter

As shown in Fig. 1, the detector consists of the angle filter in direct combination with the sensor. The main characteristics of the detector are its dynamic range (of more than 8 orders of magnitude), a uniform sensitivity (<5 %) over the entire detector area, and a suitable and known spectral response (shown in Fig. 3b). In the prototype the detector is realized by a silicon-based large-area detector.

The sensor surface must be completely covered with a flat angular filter that meets the angular selectivity and geometric requirements of a near field goniophotometer, which are defined in [16]. Over the whole

Fig. 2. Photograph (left) and schematic layout of the proof-of-concept setup (right).

Fig. 3. a (left). Spectral irradiance distribution of the light source. b (right). Spectral response of the sensor/detector

area of the detector, the angle filter selects incident rays which are in the angular range of $\theta \pm \Delta\theta_{\max,AF}$ and $\varphi \pm \Delta\varphi_{\max,AF}$, where θ and φ are the detection angles and $\Delta\theta_{\max,AF}$ or $\Delta\varphi_{\max,AF}$ are the acceptance angles of the angular filter. In our case, all other rays are absorbed by the chosen filter material. The angle filter used in the prototype provides a non-flat angle selectivity curve of finite width, which is shown in Fig. 4.

3. Comparison near field measurements with one-axis far field measurements

3.1. Description of sample

To test the novel measurement approach, its results are compared to those of conventional far field measurements. For these comparative measurements, a 4 mm thick clear float glass with a homogeneous and isotropic white print over its entire frontside surface is used. The printed side faces the light source.

The strong scattering of light reflected by the paint on the glass surface is expected to result in a forward lobe that is wide enough to be resolved by the instrument.

Due to the sample's microscopically small, homogeneously distributed white printing pigments, no local differences in the transmission properties are found and the same transmittance values can be expected for small (far field goniometer) and large (near field goniometer) measuring spots. While this sample does not resemble a typical application case for the new test setup, as it does not show any extended structures, it serves perfectly well for comparative measurements.

3.2. Measurements

The conventional far field measurements are performed with a *Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050* spectrophotometer equipped with an *automated reflectance/transmittance analyser (ARTA)* accessory. A 4 cm × 4 cm sample piece is irradiated with a 5 mm × 7 mm measuring spot using a collimated light beam and perpendicular incidence. Initially, it has been verified that a variation in the azimuthal detection angle has no influence on the angle-dependent transmittance values, which is the case due to the isotropy of the sample. While using a fixed azimuthal detection angle φ , the polar detection angle θ was varied by moving the detector in 2.5° steps.

The detector aperture corresponds to a patch size covering solid angles corresponding approximately to cones with opening angles $\Delta\theta$ and $\Delta\varphi$ of $\pm 5^\circ$. In addition, an integrating sphere was used to measure the hemispherical transmittance for vertical incidence, with which the angle-dependent transmittance values were weighted to achieve consistency with the absolute transmittance values integrated over all angles. Transmission spectra were detected in 10 nm steps in the VIS-IR (up to 1200 nm) spectral range. Based on those values, spectrally integrated transmittance values were calculated. To be able to compare these with the spectrally integrated transmittance values of the near field setup, the

integrals, which were derived with the far field setup, were weighted with the spectral intensity distribution of the light source in the near field setup and with the spectral response of the near field detector using

$$\tau_{\text{far field, weighted}} = \frac{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} \tau_{\text{far field}}(\lambda) \cdot E_{\text{enear field}}(\lambda) \cdot SR_{\text{near field}}(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_1}^{\lambda_2} E_{\text{enear field}}(\lambda) \cdot SR_{\text{near field}}(\lambda) d\lambda} \quad (1)$$

with

$\tau_{\text{far field, weighted}}$ – spectrally integrated and weighted transmittance value,

$\tau_{\text{far field}}(\lambda)$ – wavelength dependent transmittance values measured with the far field setup,

$E_{\text{enear field}}(\lambda)$ – wavelength dependent irradiance of the light source used in the near field setup [W/m^2],

$SR_{\text{near field}}(\lambda)$ – wavelength dependent spectral response of the detector used in the near field setup [A/W],

$\tau_{\text{near field}}$ – integral transmittance values determined with the near field setup.

An analogous measurement of the spectrally integrated angular dependent and hemispheric transmittance values was performed with the near field setup measurement as described in Section 2, where a larger sample piece (16 cm × 20 cm) of the identical material was used. The effective solid angle covered by the detector, which is defined by the sensitivity curve of the angle filter (Fig. 4), is smaller than the one in the case of the conventional far field setup. Thus, the measured angle-dependent transmittance values were weighted with the effective solid angles corresponding to a detector aperture with opening angles $\Delta\theta$ and $\Delta\varphi$ of $\pm 5^\circ$, i.e., they were evaluated as if they were measured with a detector aperture identical to the one applied on the far field setup. In this way, the results measured with both setups were made comparable.

3.3. Results: comparison of near field measurements and far field measurements

Fig. 5 compares the angle-dependent transmittance values derived with both methods. The results agree well, and the results obtained with the new near field goniophotometer method lie well inside the maximum measurement uncertainty range of commercial conventional devices, which is 0.03 % absolute (provided by the device supplier). Furthermore, it can be observed that even smaller transmittance values, as they occur for larger angles $\theta > 70^\circ$, can be measured with the new setup. The deviation from the results obtained with the conventional setup increases for polar detection angles between approximately 60° to 80° . Between 80° and 82.5° a discontinuity can be found in the conventional goniophotometer measurement. Similarly, at 10° , an unexpected value was measured. These are most probably due to the fact that the motion of the goniometer was hindered because of mechanical issues with the stepper motor.

Fig. 4. The sensitivity curve of the angle filter (left) represented through concentric rings (right) of the detector. The comparative representation of sensitivity is shown through the red and green (dotted) lines in both figures. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. (left) Visible effect of the white glass showing mostly diffuse transmittance on the screen behind the sample. On the photo the sample is illuminated with a red laser pointer. The bright ring appearing on the front-side of the glass is due to internal back reflection and also shows the rather uniform diffuse behavior of the sample. (right) Angle-dependent transmittance values of the white glass derived with the new near field test setup, see Fig. 2, and with a conventional far field goniophotometer. The spectrally integrated and weighted transmittance values are determined for various polar angles θ using a fixed azimuthal detection angle φ (sample with azimuthal isotropy) and normal incidence. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4. Comparison near field measurement vs. simulation

4.1. Description of samples and measurement setup

The samples used for the comparison of near field measurements with raytracing simulation are based on a custom lamella arrangement shown in Fig. 6 and represent a typical Venetian blind system. The individual slats of the samples are 10.6 mm wide and 120 mm long and are arranged at an axial distance of 18.33 mm from each other. There is no curvature and the slat thickness is approximately 0.5 mm. Each slat can be rotated around its longitudinal axis by a defined tilt angle.

Generally, the angle-dependent transmittance of samples with extended structures, like the lamella setup, depends on the geometry and physical design of the sample but also on the optical properties of the materials used, i.e., their scattering properties. Therefore, three different slat materials were used to compare simulation with experimental results, i.e., grey, black and mirror-like reflecting lamella materials. The optical properties, together with the geometry, serve as input parameters for the simulation models. The black and mirror-like reflecting samples serve as two examples where the geometry clearly dominates the transmittance behavior compared to the impact of the local optical properties.

Fig. 6. Sample installed on the near field goniophotometer, CAD model used in simulation (center), definition of slat angle and corresponding situation on a vertical façade (right).

In the case of black lamellas, it is expected that no or only very minor angle-dependent effects are observed when changing the tilt of the lamellas, as almost all incident light on the slats is absorbed. The transmittance can thus be quantified by purely shading considerations. On the other hand, the mirror-like reflecting slats will reflect almost all light incident on the slats directionally. The angle of reflection of the slat is thus directly determined by the tilt angle while there will be no or only minor contributions from diffuse reflection. Thus, one can expect two transmittance peaks in this case: one corresponding to the light that passes the sample directly without reflection at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and a second one at an angle θ defined by the tilt angle. The grey slats represent an intermediate case, showing some diffuse reflection in addition to the direct shading.

4.1.1. Optical properties of grey slats

The BRDF of the grey slats was measured on a pab gonio-photometer pg2¹ at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts, operating under far field conditions and scanning the reflection hemisphere at adaptive, high-directional resolution. A Xenon arc lamp was employed during the measurement. Focused on the detector to achieve maximum angular resolution, a circular area of approximately 20 mm diameter under normal incidence was irradiated on the sample. The irradiated area forms the sampling aperture over which the measurement is averaged since the detectors (Si-based approx. 300 nm–1100 nm, InGaAs approx. 1200 nm–2000 nm) have a wider field of view. The resulting instrument signature, which limits the resolution of specular reflection in the measurement, has a FWHM of approximately 1 degree.

Using the two detectors, BRDFs in the spectral range covered by the novel near field instrument and the infrared were acquired for eight incident polar angles ($\theta' = 10^\circ$ – 70° at intervals of 10° , and 82.5°). The acquired BRDF was exported in a tabular format following the recommendations of ASTM E-2387:19 [7].

The assumption of rotational isotropic reflection was tested by carrying out measurements for polar angles $\theta' = 10^\circ$, 40° , and 70° and for two azimuthal angles, i.e., $\phi' = 0^\circ$ and $\phi' = 90^\circ$. The corresponding direct-hemispherical reflectance values of $\rho = 0.676$, 0.681 , and 0.739 for $\phi' = 0^\circ$, and $\rho = 0.668$, 0.675 , and 0.736 for $\phi' = 90^\circ$ respectively, were solved by integration of the BRDF over all detection angles. The assumption of rotational isotropic reflection was confirmed, as only low relative differences of the direct-hemispherical reflectance integrals were found (1.2 % for $\theta' = 10^\circ$, 0.9 % for $\theta' = 40^\circ$, 0.4 % for $\theta' = 70^\circ$). The measured BRDF is illustrated for $\phi' = 0^\circ$ and $\theta' = 10^\circ$, 40° , and 70° with their corresponding direct-hemispherical reflectance integrals in Fig. 7. The curves for $\phi' = 90^\circ$ are not plotted as the differences are too small to visualize.

4.1.2. Optical properties of the mirror slats

The hemispherical optical properties of the mirror slats were determined with the same *Perkin Elmer Lambda 1050* setup as for the white-printed glass in Section 3.2. It is found that the reflectance is rather independent of the wavelength with values between 70 % and 95 %, see Fig. 8 (left). The oscillations that can be seen for the mirror-like lamella are due to thin layers on the surface of the slats. The mirror effect can be clearly observed in the setup, Fig. 8 (right), where the direct transmission as well as the transmission through reflection at higher angles depending on the lamella tilt become visible. It is worth noting that in the general case of slats with non-zero reflectivity, the θ -dependence of the transmittance varies if the azimuthal angle ϕ is modified.

4.1.3. Optical properties of the black slats

The measurement of the optical properties of the black slats showed an absorption value of 92 % and a reflectance of 8 % (Fig. 8, left). In

Fig. 7. Illustration of the spectrally integrated BRDF of grey slats measured at $\theta' = 10^\circ$, 40° , and 70° and $\phi' = 0^\circ$ in the range of 300 nm–1100 nm. The y-axis shows the BRDF scaled by the cosine of the reflection angle, which corresponds to the reflected radiance over the irradiance on the sample. The polar angle θ on the x-axis is the angle of the detector of reflection with respect to the negative z-axis.

contrast to the mirror slats, significant transmittance is only expected at a single angle of $\theta = 0^\circ$.

4.2. Simulation approach

The simulation model that was developed for the measurement of transmittance of the test sample replicates the measurement setup as described in Section 2. The simulation model and subsequent calculations are implemented with the Radiance raytracing system [12]. Radiance is an open-source software that implements backward-raytracing to compute the radiative transfer between luminous surfaces and measurement points.

While estimating optical properties of glazing and fenestration systems through far field photometric approaches has been done before within Radiance (using the *genBSDF* program) [13], there are no established simulation models to estimate transmittance through near field photometry. Therefore, a custom simulation model has been developed.

As mentioned above, the principle behind the measurement of transmittance for a given sample is based on estimating the amount of radiant energy (power) transmitted through the sample. However, several adjustments have to be made when replicating the measurement process with its specific real-world properties. With reference to Fig. 1, which describes the measurement set-up, the following approaches have been used in the simulation:

- **Light source:** The light source is conceptualized in terms of rays in the simulation, with each ray possessing an origin and a direction. The light rays maintain uniform energy across all spectral bands (i.e., in the three RGB channels of the Radiance simulation) and each ray is assigned equal weight. The origin of each light ray is determined by randomly sampling a position within Surface 1, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The direction is derived from the incident angle of the light source.
- **Maximum angular divergence of the light source:** The rated divergence of the actual light source ($\Delta\theta_{LS}$ and $\Delta\phi_{LS}$) is incorporated by distributing the direction of light rays according to a Gaussian distribution that deviates in the range of $\pm\Delta\theta_{LS}$ and $\pm\Delta\phi_{LS}$. For each origin of rays in the light source, up to 10,000 light ray directions, based on the specified Gaussian distribution, were considered in the simulation.
- **Optical properties of the sample:** The optical properties of the slat materials (as described above) are used in Radiance as follows:

¹ pab advanced technologies Ltd., Freiburg im Breisgau, Germany. <https://www.pab.eu/>.

Fig. 8. (left) Hemispherical reflectance data of mirror-like and black slat materials. (right) Sample consisting of mirror-like slats placed under the light source of the new near field setup showing the transmittance at polar angles $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\theta > 0^\circ$ in dependence on the lamella tilt angle.

- Grey slats: BSDF material data based on measurements at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts were used. (*Radiance input: void BSDF grey 6 0.000 BIMSOL179_Vis_g8_+a.xml 0.010 0.010 1.000. 0 0*)
- Mirror slats: Reflectance values, as determined by hemispherical measurement, were used in Radiance mirror primitive. (*Radiance input: void mirror mirrors 0 0 3 0.827 0.916 0.927*)
- Black slats: Diffuse reflectance of 8 % was assumed for the black lamella without further measurement. (*Radiance input: void plastic black 0 0 5 0.08 0.08 0.08*)
- *Geometry and placement of the sample:* The geometry of the sample is represented using polygons. As in the CAD model shown in Fig. 6, the placement of the sample is achieved through an opaque surface with a circular opening. The circular opening acts as the aperture for the transmission of light through the sample.
- *Location of the detector:* The polar and azimuthal angular positions of the detector (θ , φ) are the same as in the measurement and are kept constant for all simulations.
- *Angle filter:* The angle filter is not modeled physically in the simulation. It is represented through a virtual surface that jointly

represents the detector and the angle filter. The virtual surface consists of an arrangement of concentric rings. The sensitivity of the rings is based on the sensitivity curve of the angle filter.

4.3. Results: Comparison of near field measurements and simulation

This section presents pairwise comparisons of transmittance values between measurement results with the near field goniophotometer and the raytracing simulation results according to the above-described approach. The incidence angle of the light source was in normal direction to the sample and fixed at all times in the measurement as well as in the simulation. Figs. 9–11 provide results of measured and simulated transmittance values for the three lamella samples (black, grey, and mirror slats) with different slat angles. The polar angle θ was varied over a certain range (x-axis) for specific azimuthal angles φ .

Fig. 9a and b show the comparison of transmittance values for the black lamella for two different slat angles: 0° , corresponding to fully open slats (Fig. 9a), and 90° , corresponding to fully closed slats (Fig. 9b). Transmission occurred only at low polar angles θ . Beyond $\theta = 15^\circ$, no transmission was found in both simulation and measurement. A high

Fig. 9a. Black lamella with slat angle 0° . Values are shown for $\varphi = 0^\circ$ (left) and for $\varphi = 90^\circ$ (right).

Fig. 9b. Black lamella with slat angle 90°. Values are shown for $\varphi = 0^\circ$ (left) and for $\varphi = 90^\circ$ (right).

Fig. 10a. Grey lamella with a slat angle of 20° and $\varphi = 0^\circ$. (Right graph zooms in to better visualize the comparison).

agreement between measurement and simulation can be stated for both slat angles, with the fully open slats showing high transmittance values for low polar angles below $\theta = 15^\circ$. In this case, the effects of the non-ideal angle filter and light source become apparent. The ideal case would result in a very sharp peak centered at $\theta = 0^\circ$. The finite width of the peak is due to the small divergence of the light source and the acceptance angle range of the angular filter, which is around $\pm 3^\circ$ for each of these two contributions. In conventional goniophotometer measurements, this error would be caused by the effects of the finite detector distance from the sample in comparison to the measurement spot and detector size. Closed slats still allow light to transmit due to the

specific geometry as can also be seen in Fig. 9b. No change was noticed when the sample was rotated by 90°.

Fig. 10a and b compare simulation and measurement for grey slats with a slat angle of 20°. Similar to the black slats, high transmittance values only occur for low polar angles. Again, this peak at $\theta = 0^\circ$ is widened due to the small divergence of the light source and the non-ideal angular filter. Also, due to the slightly inclined slats, less direct radiation can penetrate through the sample. In consequence, the maximum transmittance value at $\theta = 0^\circ$ is found to be slightly above 70 % (compared to 90 % for the horizontal slats in Fig. 9a). A rotation of the sample by 10° (from $\varphi = 0^\circ$ to $\varphi = 10^\circ$) does not influence transmittance

Fig. 10b. Grey lamella with a slat angle of 20° and $\varphi = 10^\circ$. (Right graph zooms in to better visualize the comparison.)

Fig. 11. Mirror lamella with a slat angle of 20° . Values are shown for $\varphi = 0^\circ$ (left) and for $\varphi = 90^\circ$ (right).

significantly at first glance. However, when zooming in, some differences are found at higher polar angles (from $\theta = 15^\circ$ to $\theta = 65^\circ$) although the absolute transmittance stayed below 1 %. The comparison shows how well the measured angle-dependent transmittance can be reproduced by simulation even at very low transmittance values.

Fig. 11 shows the mirror lamella with a slat angle of 20° . The transmittance at $\theta = 0^\circ$ is the same as for the grey slat system, as it is driven by the direct radiation passing through the blinds. Due to the high reflectance of the slat surface, a specular transmittance effect can be noticed. The reflection on the slats led to a second transmittance peak at $\theta = 40^\circ$. In both cases, measurement and simulation, the peak occurred at $\theta = 40^\circ$ and flattened within $\pm 8^\circ$ of the peak. This peak width is related to (a) the divergence of the light source and the non-ideality of the angular filter, and (b) minor diffuse stray light contributions of the

mirror-like material. The maximum transmittance at this secondary peak was found to be around 19 % in the measurements and 29 % in the simulation. This difference might be caused by varying surface properties and/or polarization effects that are not covered in the simulation model. Also, the actual reflectance of the real sample (see Fig. 8) was impacted by slight pollution, while in the simulation, a perfect mirror type was assumed.

Finally, the angular filter applied in the simulation method is a model only representing the key characteristics of a real filter. It is characterized by a Gaussian distribution describing the effective acceptance angle with no dependence on the azimuthal angle φ . However, the details, like the exact shape showing minor deviations from a Gaussian and the slight φ -dependence of the sensitivity curve of the angular filter, have not been implemented to keep the simulation efforts reasonable. When the

sample was rotated by 90° (from $\varphi = 0^\circ$ to $\varphi = 90^\circ$), the secondary peak at $\theta = 40^\circ$ disappeared in the measurement as well as in the simulation, as expected.

5. Error analysis

5.1. Analysis of measurement errors with the near-field goniophotometer

The major objective of this work was to develop and demonstrate a near-field approach to measure angular-dependent transmittance values of extended shading systems with structural elements.

A far-field measurement is characterized by a large distance $D_{PD,FF}$ between the detector and the object to be measured (see Fig. 12). In particular, the distance $D_{PD,FF}$ between object and detector needs to be much larger than the dimensions of the measured part of the object (D_A) and dimensions of detector ($D_{D,FF}$) themselves. The error in the angular measurement $\Delta\theta$ is then directly related to this ratio of object and detector dimensions to the distance between object and detector, i.e. $\Delta\theta \sim (D_{D,FF} + D_A)/(2 D_{PD,FF})$. This implies that in cases with $D_A/D_{PD,FF} \rightarrow 0$ and $D_{D,FF}/D_{PD,FF} \rightarrow 0$, all angle-related errors can be neglected.

However, in case of the presented near field setup such an assumption cannot be made. There are several sources of measurement errors that need to be considered: with the distance between object and detector ($D_{PD,NF}$) being similar to the size of the object (D_A), no selection of light rays with respect to the angle is given in contrast to the far-field measurement. Hence, the error in angle $\Delta\theta$ is not determined by the ratio $D_A/D_{PD,NF}$ anymore, but rather by the quality of the angular filter, i.e. its sensitivity curve.

Since extended objects with internal structures are to be measured, the measurement result is basically a spatial average over the size of the measured part of the sample (D_A) and the detector ($D_{D,NF}$). Thus, in contrast to the far field measurement, an extended detector with dimensions larger than the object needs to be used. This implies that non-uniformities in the laterally extended light-field and non-uniformities within the extended detector need to be considered. Also, when moving the detector to a $\theta > 0^\circ$ position, the area of the projection of the object on the detector, being related to $\cos(\theta)$, becomes smaller. Nevertheless, the detector signal still needs to be directly related to the total captured irradiance even if parts of the detector are not uniformly irradiated.

As the angular dependent measurement is a succession of multiple measurements for all needed θ -values, the temporal stability of the light source needs to be given. This concerns both the overall intensity as well as the spectral stability. Finally, the determination of the angular-dependent transmittance values requires low angular deviations of the incident light. In our case, this is related to the light-field characteristics, i.e., the divergence of the light source.

In the presented experiments, a solar simulator of class AAA according to the standard IEC 60904-9 was integrated into the setup. This implies a spatial non-uniformity below 2 %, a temporal stability under continuous illumination below 2 %, and a spectral match between 75 % and 125 %. Regarding the detector, mono-crystalline silicon solar cells were used. This solar cell technology is characterized by a very high

lateral uniformity as can be checked using, for example, electroluminescence imaging or light-beam-induced-current measurements [19]. Finally, the measurement error when determining the short circuit current of the solar cell (which is directly related to the incident light intensity on the solar cells) needs to be considered. Here, the measurement electronics is specified with an error below 1 %.

This has led to the conclusion that the major error sources in the presented work are the angle-selectivity of the angular filter and the slightly non-parallel incident light of the light source. As described in Section 2.3, the divergence of the light source has been determined to be such that 95 % of the incident light rays on the test specimen do not exceed an angular divergence of $\Delta\theta_{LS}/\Delta\varphi_{LS} = \pm 3^\circ$. On the other hand, the angular selectivity of the filter is directly related to the amount of light that passes through it. For example, a high angular selectivity can be achieved only at the cost of a strong reduction of the amount of light passing the filter. Furthermore, not only the design and dimensions of the filter, e.g., the ratio between the diameter and length of the openings in the filter, but also the material of the angular filter is relevant: a much higher angular selectivity is achieved when the filter material is highly absorbing thus reducing internal reflections within the filter. All these properties of the angular filter are described by the sensitivity curve as presented in Fig. 4. This analysis leads directly to the conclusion that a discussion of measurement errors or deviation between experiment and simulation needs to include both: variations in the measured intensity of the light leading to variations in the transmittance value and variations in the associated angle θ . From an experimental point of view, the realization of the successive detector positioning at various well-defined polar angles θ is also rather challenging. In our setup, we achieved a detector-positioning error of about 2° .

Thus, when comparing two measurements or an experiment with simulation, the relevant error is not only given by the deviations between the transmittance values but the combination between both, transmittance and polar angle. For example, if in Figs. 9–11 only the difference between the transmittance values is considered, one would obtain a larger error than if the proximity of the simulation data point to the complete experimental curve is analyzed. Also, it is noteworthy that since the transmittance is already a relative quantity, i.e., the ratio between outgoing intensity compared to incident intensity, the relevant error for a typical application is not the relative error in transmittance but rather the absolute error. For example, if the real transmittance value is very low, then even an equally low absolute error could lead to very high relative errors. However, the relevant physical quantity is the total transmitted amount of light, which is characterized by the absolute error in the transmittance rather than the relative error.

5.2. Analysis of errors implied by the simulation

The simulation software Radiance uses ray tracing to calculate the light distribution in scenes. As a stochastic process, it is therefore subject to fluctuations and deviations based on a variety of influences. One factor, for example, is the structure and discretization of the geometry of the scene. If, for example, curved surfaces such as the louvres here, are approximated by polygons, inaccuracies can occur when calculating reflections. Numerical precision also plays a role, as the calculations in ray tracing – e.g., the determination of intersection points or reflection angles – are subject to rounding errors.

The way in which light sources are modelled also influences the accuracy of the results. For example, planar light sources require integration over their surface, which results in additional sampling errors compared to simpler point light models. Furthermore, the consideration of material models affects the calculation of light interactions. Here we used a detailed model, particularly for the grey lamella, by measuring the surface reflectance using a goniophotometer. However, a simplified, Lambertian reflection behavior was assumed for the black lamella.

Stopping criteria used in ray tracing, such as limiting the recursion depth for reflections, can also cause errors. If the recursion depth is too

Fig. 12. Geometry of near field and far field setup showing the different length-scales in the two setups.

small, important light paths may be ignored. An important – if not the most important – factor is the number of rays traced. Particular care must be taken here to ensure that a sufficient number of samples is used so that scenes with complex lighting situations (e.g., high contrasts, sharp shadows) can also be reproduced correctly.

The validated [20] software Radiance can deliver reliable results if the parameters are selected appropriately. In the simulations presented above, the parameters were set accordingly high, to reduce the variation in the results. In a sensitivity analysis for the black lamella, we varied the parameters minimally to assess the influence on the results. We thereby focused on the number of initially sampled rays. The deviation in transmittance was between -1.1% and $+1.3\%$, with a maximum standard deviation of 0.7% . This shows that the chosen parameters are sufficiently high to make the simulations reliable.

5.3. Absolute and relative differences for the comparison between measurement and simulation

In the following Tables 1–6 the absolute and relative difference between measured and simulated transmittance is shown. To avoid ambiguity with relative difference, the transmittance values τ are considered in a range from 0 to 1 instead of 0 % to 100 %. The absolute difference is defined as measured transmittance minus simulated transmittance. Positive signs hence indicate that the simulated values were lower than measured ones, negative signs that simulated values were higher measured ones.

$$D_{\text{abs}} = \tau_{\text{meas}} - \tau_{\text{sim}} \quad (2)$$

with

D_{abs} Absolute difference between measurement and simulation [–1; 1].

τ_{meas} Measured value of transmittance [0; 1].

τ_{sim} Simulated value of transmittance [0; 1].

Additionally, the relative difference is shown with the definition as follows:

$$D_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\tau_{\text{meas}} - \tau_{\text{sim}}}{\frac{1}{2} \cdot (\tau_{\text{meas}} + \tau_{\text{sim}})} \quad (3)$$

with

D_{rel} Relative difference of transmittance [–200 %; 200 %].

(Note: In Tables 1–6 values for D_{rel} were not calculated for some geometries, because the prerequisite of Eq. (2) (τ value > 0) was not fulfilled in these certain geometries as a result of measurement errors.)

The mean absolute difference (or bias) was calculated as

$$\bar{D}_{\text{abs}} = \frac{1}{n} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n D_{\text{abs},i} \quad (4)$$

Standard deviation was calculated as

$$s_D = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n (D_{\text{abs},i} - \bar{D}_{\text{abs}})^2} \quad (5)$$

The mean absolute difference based on all ($n = 144$) pairs of measured and simulated transmittance values was found to be $\bar{D}_{\text{abs}} =$

-0.001774 , the standard deviation of the absolute difference was found to be $s_D = 0.016811$.

In order to visually investigate the quality of agreement, Fig. 13 shows the absolute difference (y-axis) plotted on the average value of measured and simulated transmittance, i.e., $(\tau_{\text{meas},i} + \tau_{\text{sim},i})/2$ (x-axis). As upper and lower boundary, $1.977 \cdot s_D$ is added to the graph to examine potential outliers.

Ten outliers were found. The two highlighted in red are those for $\theta = 40^\circ$ and 42.5° in the case of mirror lamella (slat angle 20° , $\varphi = 0^\circ$). The reasons for the greater deviation (surface properties, polarization) were discussed in Section 4. The remaining eight outliers correspond to the expected number for a 95 % confidence interval with $n = 144$ (degree of freedom $v = n - 1 = 143$) and their distribution does not show a specific pattern.

6. Discussion

The developed near field goniophotometer provides significant advantages over typical far field goniophotometers. In conventional goniophotometer setups, the distance between the sample and the detector must be much larger than the dimensions of measurement spot and detector in order to perform reliable angular measurements. These physical constraints directly imply that extended samples with large internal structures require very large measurement setups. The new approach features a device that by itself is relatively small compared to large goniophotometer setups, such as typically used for characterization of scattering shading devices. At the same time, the measuring spot is relatively large compared to scanning point detectors. This allows for measuring samples that have a structural pattern, such as blind shading systems or similar with a compact measurement device that does not require large laboratory spaces.

The developed prototype is easy to handle and measurements do not require major preparation time. The comparison with simulation results shows that the developed method and the applied setup are suitable for scattering samples and that scattering effects can be detected.

The authors foresee practical applications of the instrument when direct BTDF measurements on systems featuring large-scale structures, that have a significant share of shading systems in today's market, are requested rather than relying on computational methods. This can be motivated, e.g., by the aim to exclude errors due to modelling error, lack of exact information on the system geometry including deformation and manufacturing tolerances, or the need to test computational methods.

For samples with very sharp peaks, a widening of these peaks is observed due to the small divergence of the light source and the finite width of the angular selectivity curve of the detector. This can be improved by optimizing the design of the angle filter when an increase in the angular accuracy is required. In this case, finer intervals of detection polar angle will ensure that sharp maxima or similar features are not overlooked.

In its current version, the presented experimental prototype yields reliable measurement results, which have been shown to be consistent with both conventional goniophotometer measurements and simulations. At the same time, its characteristics constrain its general applicability which needs to be addressed in further developments.

First, the spectral coverage of the detector does not match the entire

Table 1

Absolute difference D_{abs} between measured and simulated transmittance values (from 0 to 1) of black lamella shown in Fig. 9a and 9b with slat angles of 0° and 90° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

D_{abs} [–1; 1]		Polar angle θ						
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15
0°	0°	–0.017	–0.013	–0.005	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.000
90°	0°	0.004	–0.045	0.016	0.021	0.011	0.005	0.000
0°	90°	0.016	0.009	0.004	–0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
90°	90°	0.004	0.032	–0.030	0.014	0.009	0.004	0.000

Table 2

Relative difference D_{rel} in percent between measured and simulated black lamella shown in Fig. 9a and b with slat angles of 0° and 90° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 90^\circ$.

D_{rel} [-200 %; 200 %]		Polar angle θ						
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15
0°	0°	0.44	4.93	-20.08	87.91	-	-	-
90°	0°	0.42	-6.80	8.70	106.03	-	-	-
0°	90°	10.62	8.59	13.64	-55.64	-	-	-
90°	90°	-11.21	-13.86	-27.72	72.89	-	-	-

Table 3

Absolute difference D_{abs} between measured and simulated transmittance values (from 0 to 1) of grey lamella shown in Fig. 10a and b with a slat angle of 20° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 10^\circ$.

D_{abs} [-1; 1]		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15	17.5	20	22.5
0°	20°	-0.013	-0.044	0.009	0.010	0.005	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.002
10°	20°	0.013	-0.022	-0.038	0.007	0.005	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	25	27.5	30	32.5	35	37.5	40	42.5	45	47.5
0°	20°	0.003	0.003	0.003	0.002	0.002	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.002	0.001
10°	20°	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	50	52.5	55	57.5	60	62.5	65	67.5	70	
0°	20°	0.001	0.000	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	-0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	
10°	20°	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	

Table 4

Relative difference D_{rel} in percent between measured and simulated grey lamella shown in Fig. 10a and b with a slat angle of 20° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 10^\circ$.

D_{rel} [-200 %; 200 %]		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15	17.5	20	22.5
0°	20°	-1.84	-9.27	6.81	83.97	178.4	136.9	73.63	40.69	47.15	51.31
10°	20°	1.79	-4.59	-36.16	64.75	182.3	143.2	67.07	17.93	-4.40	-8.92
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	25	27.5	30	32.5	35	37.5	40	42.5	45	47.5
0°	20°	55.04	56.43	46.74	34.36	26.91	26.76	28.93	33.69	34.59	30.52
10°	20°	-15.27	-18.65	-25.88	-30.29	-33.53	-32.11	-38.61	-38.68	-39.24	-42.09
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	50	52.5	55	57.5	60	62.5	65	67.5	70	
0°	20°	14.93	6.36	-38.22	-77.98	-94.74	-100.4	-75.24	-48.61	-50.00	
10°	20°	-56.30	-69.23	-73.15	-82.57	-84.46	-77.04	-70.87	-55.81	-48.28	

solar spectrum. While this can be overcome from a technical point of view by using sensors covering a wider spectral range (e.g., tandem detectors coupling different semiconductors), these solutions are costly and require more complex engineering efforts to achieve the required detector sizes.

The second limitation is the static positioning of the light source in the prototypical setup. However, this could be easily compensated for by tilting the entire sample plane relative to the light source. Nevertheless, assessing all combinations of incident angles and transmittance angles clearly increases the number of measurements and thus the total measurement time.

Finally, the selectivity curve of the angular filter and the divergence of the light source implemented in the prototype limit the angular resolution of the measurements, which leads to a widening of otherwise

sharp transmittance peaks by around $5^\circ - 7^\circ$. The angular filter could easily be modified to narrow down this range, potentially at the cost that the total intensity of the detected light decreases and the sensitivity of the detector needs to be increased. Another option would be to apply focusing optics to the detector, so that a narrow angular selectivity curve could be achieved while the detector signal remains at a reasonable level.

Similarly, the divergence of the light source can be reduced by adding a second angular filter in the incident light beam. However, this would again imply a decrease in the total light intensity, which would have to be compensated by a higher sensitivity of the detector. Consequently, in its current setup, the instrument is to be employed in domains where BTDF of moderate resolution are adequate.

Table 5

Absolute difference D_{abs} between measured and simulated transmittance values (from 0 to 1) of mirror lamella shown in Fig. 11 with a slat angle of 20° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 10^\circ$.

$D_{abs} [-1; 1]$		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15	17.5	20	22.5
0°	20°	-0.015	-0.056	-0.022	0.004	0.002	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
10°	20°	0.032	0.040	0.029	-0.003	-0.003	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	25	27.5	30	32.5	35	37.5	40	42.5	45	47.5
0°	20°	0.001	0.000	0.003	0.004	0.020	-0.057	-0.099	-0.091	-0.035	-0.001
10°	20°	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	50	52.5	55	57.5	60	62.5	65	67.5	70	
0°	20°	0.001	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
10°	20°	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

Table 6

Relative difference D_{rel} in percent between measured and simulated mirror lamella shown in Fig. 11 with a slat angle of 20° for azimuthal angles $\varphi = 0^\circ$ and $\varphi = 10^\circ$.

$D_{rel} [-200\%; 200\%]$		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	0	2.5	5	7.5	10	12.5	15	17.5	20	22.5
0°	20°	-2.10	-11.75	-18.10	43.82	-	-	-	-	-	-
10°	20°	4.59	7.66	23.86	-34.27	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	25	27.5	30	32.5	35	37.5	40	42.5	45	47.5
0°	20°	-	-	-	98.31	35.15	-34.27	-42.70	-60.04	-104.2	-39.55
10°	20°	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Polar angle θ									
Azimuthal angle φ	Slat angle	50	52.5	55	57.5	60	62.5	65	67.5	70	
0°	20°	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10°	20°	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Fig. 13. Bland-Altman-Plot to assess bias in the comparison of measured and simulated transmittance values. Orange lines represent 95 % confidence interval with $1.977 s_D$ ($s_D = 0.016811$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

7. Conclusion

The paper describes the principle of a near field goniophotometer that has been developed to provide a cost-effective measurement method to determine the angle-dependent transmittance of shading systems with extended internal structures. The general setup of the developed prototypes, as well as the requirements with respect to the light source and detector, are described.

To assess the quality of the measurement data obtained from the new device, several tests have been performed. A sample of glass with a white coating was used to compare the standard far field measurement device

with the near field goniophotometer. A blind system with varying optical properties (black, grey, and mirror) was measured and the results could be qualitatively reproduced using ray tracing simulations. The simulation model required adjustments which are described in detail.

The comparison of measurements and simulation results showed that the qualitative behavior can be reproduced. The quantitative comparison showed minor deviations in absolute transmittance when no scattering occurred. In the case of the mirror slats, the redirected, i.e., scattered radiation could be detected at the same angular position. The absolute value of transmittance differed between measurement and simulation due to two reasons: (a) to limit the modeling and simulation

efforts, some elements of the setup have been modeled by effective parameters instead of implementing all physical details of the experimental setup, and (b) the experimental data includes some measurement errors, e.g., due to the non-ideality of the investigated samples.

In summary, it can be stated that the prototypical experimental setup of the near field goniophotometer provides valid results. It is possible to examine the transmission behavior of samples with large structures such as blinds in a small measurement setup with less experimental effort than required for far field goniophotometers. The current prototype was built with comparatively inexpensive parts which may make the near field goniometer suitable for use in areas where cost is a decisive factor. However, at the current status of development a precise comparison between the accuracy achieved through conventional far field goniometers and the near field device has not yet been undertaken.

Especially in cases, where the optical properties of the materials are unknown and the geometry is difficult to reproduce in raytracing, the near field goniophotometer could be a promising solution to test the angular transmittance during the development phase of new and innovative shading solutions. The generated data can then be used as BTDF within building simulation to predict the contribution of daylighting indoors and estimate energy performance.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used EditGPT and Grammarly in order to proofread and improve the readability of the text. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication

CRedit authorship contribution statement

S. Hoffmann: Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **C. Pfau:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **S. Subramaniam:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation. **S. Deshaboina:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **C. Hagendorf:** Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **M. Alwalidi:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **D. Geisler-Moroder:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **L.O. Grobe:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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2068.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2025.118751>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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